

Development and Evaluation of an Arduino Integrated Learning Kit to Enhance Teaching and Learning in Secondary Schools

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to develop and evaluate an Arduino Learning Kit as a teaching aid for secondary school students, particularly in the subject of Design and Technology (RBT). The study explores the use of Arduino as an innovative educational tool that supports active and hands-on learning through programming, electronics, and prototyping activities. The primary objective is to design and develop an interactive Arduino-based learning kit and accompanying instructional materials to enhance students' understanding and engagement in RBT lessons. The development process is guided by the ADDIE Model, which consists of five phases: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. During the analysis phase, the needs of students and teachers are identified to determine suitable learning content and kit components. In the design and development phases, the Arduino Learning Kit is constructed using a range of sensors, modules, and electronic components to create practical and interactive learning activities. The implementation phase involves integrating the kit into classroom instruction, allowing students to apply theoretical concepts in real-world problem-solving tasks. The effectiveness of the Arduino Learning Kit is evaluated using a questionnaire to gather feedback from students and teachers regarding usability, satisfaction, and perceived impact on learning achievement. The findings are expected to demonstrate that the kit enhances students' creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills while improving their understanding of RBT concepts. This study is anticipated to provide valuable guidelines for the development of high-quality and appropriate Arduino-based teaching aids that can strengthen teaching and learning practices in secondary schools.

KEYWORDS: Arduino, Technology Integration, Learning Kits

INTRODUCTION

The development of the curriculum in Malaysia has evolved from the Old Primary School Curriculum and the Old Secondary School Curriculum, which have since been replaced by the Standard Primary School Curriculum and the Standard Secondary School Curriculum. According to Azizi (2019), teachers are individuals who are responsible for implementing curriculum policies to achieve the intended educational goals. Therefore, teachers must possess adequate knowledge and skills to ensure that the teaching and learning process in the classroom can be effectively implemented in line with these objectives.

In this context, the development of an Arduino kit equipped with various sensors serves as a valuable teaching aid for secondary school education. Arduino is a flexible and user-friendly hardware platform that enables users to design and develop a wide range of electronic projects using microcontrollers and open-source software. The integration of multiple sensors within the kit expands the range of experimental activities and practical applications, thereby providing students with meaningful hands-on learning experiences. This approach enhances students' understanding of technological concepts while fostering problem-solving skills and creativity in learning environments.

In addition, the development of an Arduino kit with sensors supports a project-based learning approach that emphasizes active learning and direct student involvement in the teaching and learning process. By enabling students to design, build, and test their own projects, this kit fosters curiosity and creativity, while also developing essential skills such as collaboration and problem-solving, which are highly valued in real-world contexts. Therefore, the use of an Arduino kit as a teaching aid in secondary schools not only provides a more practical and in-depth learning experience but also promotes the development of various academic and professional skills required in the digital era. Furthermore, insufficient equipment for practical activities can hinder effective teaching and learning processes (Radin, 2008). Through the use of this tool, students are able to enhance their understanding of science and technology, while also preparing themselves to become future leaders in fields driven by innovation and technological advancement.

The Design and Technology subject is a relatively new subject introduced to replace Integrated Living Skills. This subject represents a significant shift in learning standards, with a stronger emphasis on technology application, design thinking, and structured

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problem-solving approaches, as well as the production of student-based projects. The implementation of the new curriculum for the Design and Technology (RBT) is seen as an effort to equip students with relevant knowledge and skills needed in today's rapidly evolving world. The content of the RBT subject differs significantly from the previous KHB curriculum, making teachers' existing knowledge and skills in this subject area crucial in ensuring the achievement of learning objectives.

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In the context of secondary school education, the use of relevant, interactive, and engaging teaching aids is highly important. This is aligned with the cognitive, social, and emotional development of adolescents in today's learning environment. At the same time, technology has become an integral part of the daily lives of the younger generation. Therefore, technology-based teaching aids, such as the Arduino learning kit with sensors, are an appropriate choice to support the teaching and learning process in secondary schools. In efforts to implement the Malaysian Education Development Plan, teachers are encouraged to demonstrate teaching competencies that are aligned with ongoing curriculum changes in schools. Since Design and Technology (RBT) is a relatively new subject, teachers are required to further strengthen their knowledge and skills in order to effectively deliver the subject content. In addition, the provision of teaching aids is considered essential as a support tool during the teaching and learning process. Samni et al. (2015) also stated that the use of teaching modules can help develop students' full potential.

The development of the Arduino Kit for the electronic design subtopic, as selected in this study, is implemented as a project-based activity conducted after students have completed the topic of Technology Applications in the Form 2 RBT curriculum under the DSKP. This activity allows students to integrate and apply knowledge from previous topics while preparing for subsequent learning content. The suggested implementation time for this activity is during face-to-face instruction, depending on the teacher's creativity and classroom conditions. Overall, the development of this Arduino Kit serves as one of the instructional strategies that teachers can use to enhance students' understanding and engagement in learning.

The use of Arduino kits equipped with various sensors offers a potential solution to address this issue. Arduino is an open-source electronics platform based on user-friendly hardware and software, making it suitable for educational applications. By integrating Arduino with sensors such as temperature, light, and gas sensors into teaching aids, educators can create more interactive and engaging learning experiences. This approach enables students to conduct hands-on experiments and apply theoretical concepts in real-world contexts, thereby enhancing their understanding of science and technology. However, the development of an Arduino-based learning kit also presents several challenges. These include selecting appropriate sensors that align with learning objectives, designing instructional modules that are both engaging and easy for students to understand, and ensuring that the kit remains affordable and accessible for schools and educational institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of technology in education has become a major focus in efforts to increase student engagement and improve learning. One technology that is increasingly gaining attention in the educational context is the Arduino kit that can be programmed with various sensors. This literature review investigates past studies related to the use of multi-sensor Arduino kits as teaching aids. According to Abdul Nasir, Ismail and Mat Daud (2015), the concept and method in the design development process have great implications towards the production of quality products. This literature review investigates past studies related to the use of Arduino kits with various sensors as teaching aids. The use of Arduino kits as teaching aids has been the focus of research in the educational context in Malaysia. A study by Zulkifli et al. (2019) shows the potential of Arduino kits in increasing student engagement in science and technology learning. The results of their study show that the use of Arduino kits can stimulate students' interest in learning and strengthen their understanding of the concepts being taught. In addition, according to Jamaluddin et al. (2020) explains how Arduino kits are used as teaching aids in teaching mathematics in Malaysian schools. They found that using Arduino kits can enrich students' learning experiences and increase their understanding of complex mathematical concepts. However, a study by Rahim et al. (2021) also highlighted several challenges faced by teachers in integrating technology such as Arduino kits into the curriculum. This is because the lack of adequate training and support for teachers is one of the main obstacles that needs to be overcome to ensure the successful implementation of this technology in the educational context in Malaysia. This is because, the Design and Technology (RBT) subject is a subject that allows students to use design skills and combine them with technology. Students are also able to think critically in line with technological changes.

Teaching aids for teachers in schools are seen as a very important component in the learning and teaching process. Teaching aids are needed to improve students' understanding of learning. Previous studies have found that the use of teaching aids has a positive impact on students' academic excellence and the teaching methods practiced. The use of teaching aids not only ensures a more interactive and enjoyable learning experience for students, but also opens up space for a deeper understanding of the subjects being taught. ABM is not limited to traditional materials such as textbooks and blackboards, but also includes various mediums that activate various senses such as vision, hearing, touch and so on. This allows teachers to create a more dynamic and comprehensive learning environment, meeting the diversity of student learning styles. According to Siti Nazurana and Konaen (2012) in planning

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effective and meaningful teaching activities for students, teachers must first think about the methods and techniques that will be used. Choosing a strategy wisely can guarantee the smoothness and effectiveness of the delivery of a topic or subject

Based on a study of existing products, there are several other products and platforms used in building electronic projects. Among the popular existing products is the BASIC Stamp, which was introduced by Parallax in 1992. The BASIC Stamp uses the easy-to-understand BASIC programming language, making it a popular choice in education and small projects. According to Toibah Umi Kalsum, Dimas Aulia Trianggana and Hermawansyah (2013). BASIC STAMP is an interpreter language. This means that it will be translated into machine code when the program is executed. The positive thing is that we can give instructions on the command line, and immediately see the results. The negative thing is that it is quite slow.

In addition, microcontrollers such as the PIC Microcontroller from Microchip Technology and the AVR Microcontroller from Atmel (now owned by Microchip Technology) were also the main choice for building electronic projects before the existence of the Arduino Kit. According to, Burhan, I., Azman, A.A. & Othman, R. (2016). PIC simplifies the design of logic and control systems, allowing complex behavioral designs to be embedded into a piece of electronic instrument.

Meanwhile, understanding embedded systems is a field of study that requires deeper exposure to meet the global needs of industry needs. In addition, small computer platforms such as Raspberry Pi are also used in electronics projects. According to Syukri Gazali Suatkab, et al. (2022). To enable the design of flexible teaching aids for various scales of internet of things projects, Raspberry Pi is used in combination with Arduino Uno as the main processor and platform for programming both for microcontrollers. This product study provides an overview of the evolution of the microcontroller platform and the development of electronic projects before the emergence of the Arduino kit, and helps in understanding the needs and shortcomings of existing products which later became the basis for the development of Arduino as a project development to be used as a teaching aid. The development of this Arduino kit is also provided with its usage modules making it different from other existing products.

METHODOLOGY

The aspects that will be explained in more detail regarding the product to be developed, the software involved, the theories, the models used and the approaches related to the study conducted, namely the Development of Integrated Arduino Kit Teaching Aids for Secondary Schools. This chapter will also discuss past studies conducted by previous researchers through certain reference materials. These materials are used to help the researcher understand more clearly and be able to carry out the study conducted perfectly.

Design and Development Process

Figure 1 illustrates the design of the module development study for the Arduino Kit teaching aid for Form 2 Design and Technology subjects. In this study, the ADDIE instructional design model was selected as the main framework. This decision was made based on the practicality and suitability of the model for the development of the intended product. The use of this research design is appropriate for a large population, as it allows for the systematic interpretation of consistent data and information from respondents (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2006). The ADDIE Model provides clarity and simplicity in the development process and serves as a structured guide for the development of instructional materials, software, and learning resources. Due to its widespread use and established effectiveness in instructional design, the ADDIE Model is a suitable choice for this study. The module development process is carried out systematically through its five phases: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation.

Figure 1 The designing a module development study for Arduino Kit

Development of Teaching Aids An integrated Arduino kit was built to help teachers provide students with an understanding of the components found in the Electronic Design chapter. For this prototype model, there are several components required which consist of the design process, programming, hardware and so on in building a system. In this section, we will discuss the block diagram which has inputs, processes and outputs. The Block Diagram is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Block Diagram of Teaching Aids An integrated Arduino kit

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Figure 3 illustrates the Arduino Integrated Learning Kit developed and used in this study. The kit consists of an electronic circuit in which various components are systematically connected on a breadboard without the need for soldering, making it safe, reusable, and suitable for educational purposes. The modular design allows students to assemble and modify circuits easily while gaining practical experience in electronics and programming. The kit incorporates several sensors and modules, including the HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor, Capacitive Touch Sensor, Rain Drop Sensor, Pulse Sensor, RFID Module, MQ-2 Gas Sensor, and DHT22 Sensor. Each sensor is mounted on a black acrylic panel with clearly labeled positions to ensure organized arrangement and facilitate ease of use during classroom activities.

The breadboard serves as a temporary prototyping platform that provides electrical connections and mechanical support for the components. Jumper Wires are used to establish connections between components and the breadboard without permanent attachment. At the center of the kit, the Arduino Uno functions as the main controller, executing programs uploaded by the user to manage and coordinate all connected sensors and modules. A USB Cable is used to connect the Arduino Uno to a computer for programming and power supply. Overall, the integrated design of the Arduino Learning Kit provides a structured and user-friendly platform that supports hands-on learning in programming, electronics, and sensor applications.

Figure 3: The Arduino Integrated Learning Kits

RESEARCH FINDING

Based on Figure 4, which illustrates students' understanding of microcontrollers and microprocessors, the majority of respondents demonstrated a positive level of understanding. A total of 10 students (58.8%) selected **Agree (S)**, while 2 students (11.8%) selected **Strongly Agree (SS)**. In addition, 5 students (29.4%) chose **Not Sure (TP)**, indicating that some respondents were still uncertain about their understanding of the topic. Overall, the findings suggest that most students have a good understanding of microcontrollers and microprocessors. The combined percentage of respondents who selected Agree and Strongly Agree was 70.6%, reflecting a generally positive perception of their knowledge in this area. However, the relatively high percentage of students who selected Not Sure indicates that further reinforcement and practical exposure may be necessary to strengthen their understanding. These results also suggest that the Arduino Learning Kit has the potential to enhance students' comprehension and increase their interest in the Design and Technology (RBT) subject through more engaging and hands-on learning experiences.

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Figure 4: Distribution according to understanding of microcontrollers and microprocessors.

Based on Figure 5, which relates to students' understanding of electronic device programming, the majority of respondents showed a positive level of understanding. A total of 5 students (29.4%) selected **Agree (S)**, while another 5 students (29.4%) selected **Strongly Agree (SS)**. Meanwhile, 3 students (17.6%) chose **Not Sure (TP)**, and 4 students (23.5%) selected **Disagree (TS)**. These findings indicate that although a considerable number of students demonstrated confidence in their understanding of electronic device programming, there is still a need for further improvement. This is because several students either disagreed or were uncertain about their level of understanding. Therefore, additional instructional support and more hands-on learning activities may be necessary to strengthen students' knowledge and skills in electronic device programming.

Figure 5: Distribution of Samples According to Their Understanding of Electronic Device Programming

Based on Figure 6, which examines whether teachers form student groups according to students' abilities in specific skills, the largest proportion of respondents indicated strong agreement. A total of 3 teachers (37.5%) selected **Strongly Agree (SS)**, suggesting that grouping students based on their skill levels is a common practice among the respondents. In addition, 1 teacher (12.5%) selected **Agree (S)**. Meanwhile, 2 teachers (25.0%) chose **Not Sure (TP)**, indicating some uncertainty regarding this practice. Both **Disagree (TS)** and **Strongly Disagree (STS)** were selected by 1 teacher each, representing 12.5% respectively. Overall, these findings suggest that most teachers tend to organize students into groups according to their abilities in specific skills. However, the presence of responses in the uncertain and disagreement categories indicates that this practice is not consistently implemented by all teachers.

Figure 6: Distribution of Samples on Whether Teachers Form Student Groups Based on Students' Abilities in Specific Skills

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Based on Figure 7, which examines whether teachers consistently monitor students' progress and understanding, the majority of respondents reported strong agreement. A total of 4 teachers (50.0%) selected **Strongly Agree (SS)**, indicating that they firmly believe that teachers regularly monitor students' academic achievement and comprehension. In addition, 3 teachers (37.5%) selected **Agree (S)**, while 1 teacher (12.5%) chose **Not Sure (TP)**. No respondents selected either **Disagree (TS)** or **Strongly Disagree (STS)**. Overall, these findings clearly indicate that teachers play an active role in continuously monitoring students' progress and understanding throughout the teaching and learning process. The high percentage of positive responses (87.5%) reflects a strong commitment among teachers to ensure that students receive appropriate guidance and support to enhance their learning outcomes.

Figure 7: Distribution of Samples on Whether Teachers Consistently Monitor Students' Progress, Achievement, and Understanding

CONCLUSION

The data analysis of this study on the development of the Arduino kit as a teaching aid has provided important insights into respondents' perceptions and experiences in using the kit. Overall, most respondents showed a positive acceptance of the kit within their teaching context. They expressed willingness to integrate this technology into their curriculum as an innovative and useful learning tool. The strengths highlighted include the completeness of content, accessibility, and clarity of instructions provided. However, several weaknesses were also identified, particularly technical challenges in using the kit, such as programming difficulties and the complexity of certain concepts for some respondents. In addition, limited resources and lack of training support were also reported as significant barriers to the effective use of the kit. From the respondents' perspective, several improvements are needed, including enhanced learning content, greater project flexibility, stronger learner support, and improved reliability of the device. Therefore, although the Arduino kit has been positively received, there is still room for improvement to further enhance its effectiveness as a teaching aid. Taking into account the feedback from respondents, future development efforts should focus on addressing these limitations while maximizing the educational potential of the Arduino learning kit.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this study entitled "*Development and Evaluation of an Arduino Integrated Learning Kit to Enhance Teaching and Learning in Secondary Schools.*" The research was conducted

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independently without any financial, commercial, or personal relationships that could be perceived as influencing the outcomes, analysis, or interpretation of the findings. All data collection, analysis, and reporting were carried out objectively in accordance with academic research standards. The author also confirms that no external parties have influenced the design, methodology, or results of this study, and all efforts were made to ensure transparency, integrity, and academic honesty throughout the research process.

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